

**INNOVATIVE METHODS OF DIAGNOSING AND TREATING
VARICOSE VEINS.**

Akhmadjonov Javokhir Uktamali o'g'li

Andijan State Medical Institute assistant

Hoshimov Ilhomboy Musojon o'g'li

Andijan State Medical Institute assistant

Annotatsiya: Varikoz – bu venalarning kengayishi va deformatsiyasini ifodalovchi kasallik bo'lib, asosan oyoqlarda paydo bo'ladi. Ushbu kasallik, qon aylanishining buzilishi natijasida yuzaga keladi va ko'pincha og'riq, shish, va estetik muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Varikozni tashxislash va davolashda innovatsion usullar, bemorlarning hayot sifatini yaxshilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqolada varikozni tashxislash va davolashning zamonaviy usullari haqida so'z yuritamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: varikoz, innovatsion texnologiyalar, venografiya, bemor, davolash, vena, qon.

Аннотация: Варикозное расширение вен – заболевание, характеризующееся расширением и деформацией вен, возникающее преимущественно на ногах. Это заболевание возникает в результате нарушения кровообращения и часто вызывает боль, отек и эстетические проблемы. Инновационные методы диагностики и лечения варикозной болезни играют важную роль в улучшении качества жизни пациентов. В этой статье мы поговорим о современных методах диагностики и лечения варикозного расширения вен.

Ключевые слова: варикозная болезнь, инновационные технологии, венография, пациент, лечение, вена, кровь.

Abstract: Varicose veins is a disease characterized by dilation and deformation of veins, which occurs mainly in the legs. This disease occurs as a result of blood

circulation disorders and often causes pain, swelling, and aesthetic problems. Innovative methods in the diagnosis and treatment of varicose veins play an important role in improving the quality of life of patients. In this article, we will talk about modern methods of diagnosing and treating varicose veins.

Key words: varicose veins, innovative technologies, venography, patient, treatment, vein, blood.

INTRODUCTION.

Varicose veins are a common disease associated with problems with the circulatory system, causing the veins to expand and deform. This condition occurs mainly in the lower legs and often causes pain, swelling, pain and aesthetic problems. Varicose veins result from the weakening of the venous valves in the inner walls of the veins, causing blood to pool and dilate the veins. Varicose veins not only cause physical discomfort, but can also have a negative effect on the psychological condition of patients. This disease is associated with many factors, including genetic predisposition, overweight, lack of physical activity, pregnancy, and lifestyle such as standing or sitting for long periods of time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

If there is a family history of varicose veins, the risk of developing this disease increases. The weakness of the venous valves or the structure of the veins may be due to genetic factors. Sitting or standing for a long time, lack of physical activity can worsen venous blood circulation and lead to the development of varicose veins. Being overweight and obese puts extra pressure on the legs, which can cause varicose veins. During pregnancy, hormonal changes in the body and an increase in blood volume put additional pressure on the venous system, which can lead to the development of varicose veins. With age, the elasticity of venous valves and veins decreases, which increases the risk of varicose veins. Hormonal changes, such as taking contraceptives or menopause, can affect the venous system. Standing or sitting in one place for a long time worsens blood circulation and can cause varicose veins. Leg wounds or trauma

can damage the venous system and lead to the development of varicose veins. One or more of these reasons can lead to the development of varicose veins.[4]

Therefore, it is important to maintain a healthy lifestyle and reduce risk factors. Varicose veins, if not diagnosed and treated in time, can lead to serious complications, such as thrombosis or venous ulcers. Therefore, early detection and effective treatment of varicose veins is important. In modern medicine, innovative methods and technologies are used in the diagnosis and treatment of varicose veins, which help to improve the quality of life of patients. The process of diagnosing varicose veins consists of several stages and includes the following innovative methods. Doppler ultrasonography is used to evaluate the blood flow of veins and their condition. This method is very effective in detecting the expansion of the veins and the accumulation of blood. The digital venography method allows you to see the internal structure of the veins. With the help of digital venography, it is possible to determine the condition of the veins and the direction of the blood flow. Magnetic resonance imaging is used to study the condition of veins and blood circulation in detail. This method allows you to get a clear image of the veins. Clinical assessment is carried out by specialists based on the patient's complaints and clinical manifestations. In this process, the patient's history, symptoms, and general condition are evaluated. Innovative methods in the treatment of varicose veins include: In the endovenous laser coagulation method, the coagulation process is carried out inside the veins with the help of a laser. Laser energy is used to close the vein walls and stop the blood flow. EVLK is a minimally invasive method that provides quick recovery and less pain for patients. Using radiofrequency energy in the radiofrequency coagulation method, heat is generated inside the veins. This process is used to close the walls of the veins and stop the blood flow. The radiofrequency method is a convenient and effective treatment method for patients. [2]

Sclerotherapy is performed by injecting a sclerosant solution into a vein. A sclerosant is used to close the inner walls of the vein and stop the blood flow. Sclerotherapy is often used for small veins and capillaries. Microsclerotherapy is used in the treatment of small veins and capillaries. With microsclerotherapy, a very small

amount of sclerosing solution is injected into the vein, which causes the vein to close. If other methods are not effective, the removal or ligation of the veins may be performed. This method, unlike traditional surgical methods, is performed using modern technologies.[1]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

Modern technologies and methods are used in the process of diagnosing varicose veins. These technologies are important in determining the condition of the veins, evaluating blood circulation and determining the extent of the disease. Below are the main modern technologies used in the diagnosis of varicose veins. Doppler ultrasonography is used to evaluate the blood flow of veins and their condition. This method allows determining the speed and direction of blood flow using ultrasound waves. This method is non-invasive, gives quick and accurate results. With the help of Doppler ultrasonography, it is possible to determine the expansion of veins, blood accumulation and other problems. Color Doppler ultrasonography shows blood flow using color images. This method allows for a more accurate assessment of the condition of the veins. With the help of color images, the direction and speed of blood flow can be seen, which helps to make the diagnosis more accurate. Venography uses a contrast agent to take X-ray images of the veins. This method allows you to see the internal structure of the veins. Venography clearly shows the condition of the veins and is effective in detecting obstructions or dilatations of the blood flow. Computed tomography allows obtaining high-resolution images to assess the condition of the veins and blood circulation. Computer tomography, with the help of which clear and detailed images of the veins are obtained, which helps to make the diagnosis more accurate. Magnetic resonance imaging uses a magnetic field and radio waves to assess the condition of veins and blood circulation. This method clearly shows the internal structure of the veins. Using magnetic resonance imaging, high-resolution images are obtained and allow a detailed study of the condition of the veins. Ultrasonic phlebography is used to assess the condition of veins and monitor blood flow using ultrasound. [3]

This method is non-invasive and gives quick results. It clearly shows the condition of the veins. Phleboscopia is performed using special optical instruments to see the condition of the veins. This method is used to determine the deformation and expansion of veins. Allows you to accurately assess the appearance and condition of the veins. In the process of diagnosing varicose veins, modern technologies play an important role in determining the condition of veins and evaluating blood circulation. Doppler ultrasonography, color Doppler, venography, CT, MRI and other methods help to make an accurate diagnosis of varicose veins. It is important to consult with specialists when choosing the most suitable diagnostic method for each patient.[5]

CONCLUSION.

Varicose veins are one of the common problems in modern medicine. Innovative methods in diagnosis and treatment are important in improving the quality of life of patients. Modern methods such as ultrasonography, laser coagulation, radiofrequency coagulation and sclerotherapy allow effective treatment of varicose veins. The most important aspect for patients is the faster recovery and less discomfort with these methods. Innovative approaches to the treatment of varicose veins play an important role in maintaining the health of patients and improving their quality of life.

REFERENCES.

1. Injection sclerotherapy for varicose veins. de Ávila Oliveira R, Riera R, Vasconcelos V, Baptista-Silva JC. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2021;12:0.
2. Nonthermal endovenous procedures for varicose veins: a health technology assessment. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34211617/> *Ont Health Technol Assess Ser.* 2021;21:1–188.
3. Varicose veins. Piazza G. *Circulation.* 2014;130:582–587.
4. Current best practice in the management of varicose veins. Whiteley MS. *Clin Cosmet Investig Dermatol.* 2022;15:567–583.
5. The epidemiology of chronic venous insufficiency and varicose veins. Beebe-Dimmer JL, Pfeifer JR, Engle JS, Schottenfeld D. *Ann Epidemiol.* 2005;15:175–184.

6. Clinical and genetic determinants of varicose veins. Fukaya E, Flores AM, Lindholm D, Gustafsson S, Zanetti D, Ingelsson E, Leeper NJ. *Circulation*. 2018;138:2869–2880.